

Process Flow Diagram

Figure 1: This figure outlines the sequence of actions in response to smartphone theft, highlighting the most common chain of technical and social actions performed. Every distinct line color represents a single chain of actions performed by participants. The *red* nodes represent non-technical actions while the *teal* nodes represent technical actions. For example, some participants start off by calling their family, then contacting their bank or wireless carrier and finally activating Lost Mode. These sequences highlight the diversity in how participants respond to theft. Some acted with technical interventions (e.g., location tracking, remote wipe), while others prioritized social steps (e.g., notifying family, filing a police report). The order and presence of actions vary depending on context, awareness, and available resources.